

**SOCIO-ECONOMIC RELATIONS IN KARAKALPAKSTAN IN THE SECOND
HALF OF THE 19TH CENTURY**

Torebaeva Nargiza

*3rd year student of Faculty of History,
Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz.*

Abstract: *In the article examined, process of development of economic-cultural trade agriculture and specialization of commodity production of national economy of Karakalpakstan in the second half of XIX century for the need of industry of tsar's Russia*

Keywords: *to trade, despotic, raw material, industry, commodity, agriculture administrative, social, economy, system tsar's Russia.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7730015>

In the second half of the 19th century, the economy of Karakalpakstan underwent the most significant changes, and contributed to the accelerated growth of commodity-money relations and the emergence of capitalist structures. In the second half of the 19th century, Russian capital began to actively penetrate Karakalpakstan. The main sphere of its application was the extraction and processing of minerals, the richness of which distinguished the subsoil of the region, as well as the industry for processing agricultural raw materials and trade. The colonial position of Karakalpakstan led to its gradual transformation into a market for industrial goods in Central Russia and a source of cheap raw materials. Commercial agriculture began to develop, enterprises of the capitalist type appeared in the food and manufacturing industries, the number of trading establishments increased, new villages and cities grew, dirt roads began to be laid. The growth of commodity production was also facilitated by the gradual settling of nomads and their transition to arable farming. The development of domestic and foreign trade in the Amu Darya department stimulated the disintegration of patriarchal-feudal relations and the penetration of capitalist relations. This is evidenced by the involvement of Karakalpak farms in trade relations, the emergence of fair, market and stationary trade, the emergence of new shopping centers, as well as the strengthening of trade relations between the Karakalpaks and neighboring regions of Central Asia, Kazakhstan, and especially Russia. The increasing transformation of Karakalpakstan, like the whole of Central Asia, into a raw materials appendage of the Russian Empire and its gradual involvement in international trade had a great impact on agriculture, socio-economic relations and the life of the population. The main commercial crop in crop production was cotton. The cities of Kungrad and Khodjeyli played an important role in the development of trade. These cities received goods from many regions of Russia and Kazakhstan.

Russian trading capital penetrated into the most remote regions of the region, even more closely linking cotton farms and local cattle breeding with the markets of Russia, Central Asia, and Western Europe. The main direction of the economic policy of tsarism after the conquest

of Central Asia by Russia was the transformation of this region into a raw material base and a market for the textile and other industries of the metropolis. In order to obtain cheap raw materials for the industry of the metropolis and create an additional market for its products, the tsarist government took a number of measures in the field of land and water use. In 1884, on July 27, the charter of the "Central Asian Commercial and Industrial Association of N. Kudrin and Co" was approved, which was allowed to arrange and maintain cotton plantations, trade in American seeds, tools and implements. The shareholders of the partnership were 53 large firms and entrepreneurs. The partnership in 1884 began work with a fixed capital of 400,000 rubles, and by 1886 had already brought this capital to 2 million rubles and they had offices with warehouses in Tashkent, Kokand, Bukhara, Chardzhou, Orenburg, Khorezm, Petro-Alexandrovska and in a number of cities of Persia. At the end of the 19th century, cotton growing became a profitable sector of the economy and played a leading role in the economy of the Amu Darya department.

During this period, due to the almost complete cessation of the import of foreign cotton, the demand for Turkestan raw cotton increased even more. He now went not only to civilian, but also to military needs. Agents of Russian trading and industrial firms began to arrive in the Amu Darya department, branches and offices of these firms were opened. In the 70-80s of the 19th century, trade operations in the department were carried out by merchants and manufacturers Konshin, Morozov, Baranov, Pavlov and others, who were attracted here by the markets for the manufactory and the region's opportunities for the production of raw cotton. In the Amu Darya department, merchants Salimzhanov, Ravilov, Brodsky and Shirman with the Armenian firm Andre-Kaspian, as well as Orenburg and other merchants who came for raw materials were engaged in the transportation of industrial goods from Central Russia.

Of great progressive importance for the entire Khorezm oasis was the Amu Darya flotilla, which gave the oasis access to the railway, linking it with Central Russia. By the end of the 90s of the 19th century, there were 23 factory enterprises in the Amu Darya department, with a total annual production of goods for 390 thousand pounds. By 1907, the department operated 135 oil mills and 84 flour mills. Most of the plants and factories belonged to the agents of the firms of Central Russia "Partnership of the Big Yaroslavl Manufactory", "Moscow Commercial and Industrial Partnership", "Partnership of the Shuiskaya Manufactory". Their shareholders were local entrepreneurs P. Manuilov, G. Ravilov, S. Aminov, I.P. Pershin, B. Allakulov, Z. Rakhmanbergenov, T. Salimzhanov, I. Bakaliev and S. Aliyev. They, together with the branch of the Russian-Asian Bank in Urgench, conducted commercial and industrial operations in cities and rural areas .

An equally valuable crop was the mulberry tree, which was used by the Karakalpakhs initially as a building material for the manufacture of individual parts of the yurt, and after the conquest of Tsarist Russia for the development of sericulture. In the Amu Darya department, 335 farms were engaged in sericulture. [9, l. 93] The buyers had storage points at the factories, in which they collected purified raw material. The products were collected in large warehouses owned by Russian merchants. In addition to cotton, 97,100 of various goods were exported annually from the Amu Darya department: alfalfa seeds, sericulture products, raw animal skin, sheep skins, butter, wool, astrakhan fur, and carpets.

Cotton and leather were transported to Moscow and the Nizhny Novgorod fair, wool to the cities of the middle Volga region, alfalfa seeds to Hamburg and North America, carpets to Turkey, butter to Baku, fish to Orenburg. The Amudarya department, like the whole of Central Asia, was not only an agricultural raw material base, but also a very profitable market for the industrial products of tsarist Russia. Trading houses of Khludov, Pervushin, Trubchaninov and others began to open in the Amu Darya department, which successfully began to compete with local merchants. Active participants were large monopolistic associations, groups and firms of the Bolshaya Yaroslavl Manufactory commercial and industrial partnership, the Krafte, Knopy, and Brothers Manuilov firms, which were engaged in buying up cotton.

About 3,000 poods of oil and other products were exported from Karakalpakstan every year. In the trade in agricultural products, imported and exported goods, agricultural products: cotton, alfalfa, wool, and leather played an important role. The entire fishery of the Aral Sea was in the hands of a major Orenburg merchant Makeev, and fish products were sent through Kazalinsk to the central cities of Russia. In Karakalpakstan, a joint-stock company "Khiva" was organized, uniting Astrakhan and Caucasian fish merchants. At least 30 fisheries with a thousand catchers were formed on the eastern shore of the Aral Sea. The material for the manufacture of the boat was thin poplar boards, for a smooth net, local Turkish - kendir yarn was used. Linen yarn for the fishing net was ordered from the Moscow textile factory, key tackle from the Nizhny Novgorod factory, and cluster boats from Orenburg. From the southern regions of the Amu Darya department, various goods were brought to Kungrad, made by masters of handicraft products from wood yurts and dairy products, and sheep and camels for sale.

Thus, the study of the historical and cultural cooperation of peoples differs in that the way of life and culture of peoples today began to be studied in a complex and continuous connection. At this stage, scientists strive to approach the study of a particular problem in a comprehensive manner, that is, they will find out the origins, reveal the value, the relationship of life, culture and other spheres of life.

Literatures:

1. Galkin M.N. Ethnographic and historical materials on Central Asia and the Orenburg region of St. Petersburg. M. 1898, p.285.
2. Demidov A.P. Economic essays on cotton growing and the cotton trade industry. Tashkent, 1926. p.234.
3. History of the Karakalpak ASSR. Tashkent. "Fan" Uz SSR, 1986, p.123.
4. Lunin B.V. To the description of the folk craft of the Karakalpaks. / Bulletin of the KKFAN UzSSR, Nukus, 1967, No. 4, p.136.
5. Peoples of Central Asia and Kazakhstan. T.1. M. 1962. p.451.
6. Sadykov A.S. Economic relations between Khiva and Russia in the second half of the 19th - early 20th centuries. Tashkent. 1965. p. 133.